

Nano-cars: The Ultimate Challenge to Automotive Industry

M. T. Michalewicz

CSIRO Supercomputing Support Group,
CSIRO Mathematical and Information Sciences
723 Swanston Street, Carlton, Victoria 3053, Australia
marek@cmis.csiro.au

Abstract

The construction of the smallest possible car, a nano-car, is proposed. The size of this engineering artifact (as the name suggests) would be $\sim 10^{-9}$ m. This is billion times smaller than so popular street machines. The necessary structural elements are: four 'Ferric wheels', 'staffenes', graphitic sheets and as a reinforcing elements – buckytubes. The novel feature of this design is the propelling system: it is embedded in the (antiferromagnetic) wheels which interact magnetically with the 'road', or atomic substrate. The actual assembly procedure details are left to the technologists. The scientific, technological and social implications of this invention are discussed; in particular its use for transportation of buckyballs in the construction of 'buckyball pyramids'. Applications in very large scale ($\sim 10^6$ cars) Intelligent Vehicle Systems and big cities traffic simulators are also outlined.

Keywords: nano-technology, nano-car, challenges, magnetic drive systems, ferric wheel

Motto: *If it was easy we would not attempt to do it.*

Marek T. Michalewicz

1 Introduction

Since the time Richard Feynman speculated on the possibility of miniaturisation of "ordinary" machines on the molecular scale of nano-metres [1] the new branch of speculative activity firmly anchored in exact sciences of physics, chemistry, molecular biology, and computer sciences have appeared. It is called nano-technology. This field achieved certain maturity and respectability based on seminal works of K. Eric Drexler [2], but still remains somewhat controversial.

There is lot to be learned from and within the nano-technology. The ideas familiar or borrowed from biochemistry, molecular biology, colloid science and micro-electronics can perhaps be extended or applied in the context of nano-technology. Unfortunately purely speculative constructs, which have no basis in physical laws (a necessary feature stressed by Feynman in his original paper [1]) find their way to popular writings, thus

undermining serious and scientific basis of nano-technology [3].

It is author's strong conviction that it will be *novel electronic, optical and transport* properties of nano-structures which would make *nano-electronic* systems attractive and useful in host of future applications [4]. However, it is interesting to explore the *mechanical* analogues of real life mechanisms in the limits of nano-meters. To this end in this paper we propose all construction elements necessary to build a nano-car. The idea of a tiny little car first surfaced in the original Feynman's paper [1]. However Feynman speculated on a micro-car, a car approximately only 4,000 times smaller than an automobile. In the present work we push the limit as far as "molecularly possible" and propose construction of a nano-car, with linear dimensions of the order $\sim 30\text{\AA} \times 20\text{\AA} \times 20\text{\AA}$. We strive to adhere to the basic laws of physics so this tiny engineering artifact can indeed be build one day.

In the next section we list and describe all required molecular "sub-parts". In the third section we touch upon the construction process and cost analysis. In section four we describe one of the most innovative feature on a nano-car - its drive system. In section five, the most speculative part of this discourse, we list some prospective applications of a nano-car. We conclude with some general remarks on a sociological impact of this engineering feat.

2 Molecular Ingredients

There would be no car, nor a cart without a wheel. Drexler [2] constructed some diamondoid circular structures for his prototypes of molecular ball bearings. What we are proposing is different. The wheels of a nano-car will be four molecules $[Fe(OMe)_2(O_2CCH_2Cl)]_{10}$, affectionately called "a molecular ferric wheel" [5].

Figure 1. A ball and stick representation of a "Molecular Ferric Wheel". Black balls are Fe ions.

A molecular ferric wheel has $\sim 17\text{\AA}$ external diameter, with internal circular “hole” of diameter $\sim 2\text{\AA}$. By cleaving or replacing *Cl* atoms on the circumference of a ferric wheel a smoother “nano-thread” should be possible.

The axles will be conveniently obtained from $[n]$ *Staffenes*, a molecular-size tinkertoys synthesized and described in detail by J. Michl, his co-workers and others [5-12]. Two examples of $[n]$ *Staffenes*, oligomer of [1.1.1]*propellane*, $n = 6$ and [6]*cubane* are depicted on Figure 2a and 2b below.

Figure 2. A ball representation of (a) oligomer of [1.1.1]*propellane*, $n = 6$ (left) and (b) [6]*cubane* (right).

The length of axle is $\sim 22\text{\AA}$ and $28\text{\AA}$ respectively. The diameter in the widest place is $\sim 6\text{\AA}$ and in the most narrow is $\sim 2\text{\AA}$, for both. The narrowing “neck” of $[n]$ *Staffene* is commensurate in diameter with the “hole” in a ferric wheel. The widening part on both sides of a “neck” forms a “collar” stabilising the structure and stopping a wheel from slipping out of an axle.

The remaining elements of nano-car construction set will be a graphitic sheet forming 2D analogue of metal-sheet joining two axles together, and perhaps some nanotubes which would provide greater structural rigidity and strength. Figure 3 represents a small fragment of a graphitic sheet.

3 Construction Procedure and Cost Analysis

The assembly of a nano-car is an issue which is best left to technologists and engineers to sort out. Suffice it to say that the use of abstraction molecular tools [14] could be the preferred choice of a fabrication technique. Since the estimate number of atoms necessary to construct a nano-car is of the order of $\sim 700 - 1000$ it is not weight of materials (some ~ 0.01 attogram) which will determine the cost of a unit. It will be the cost of processes involved in synthesis of components (axles, wheels, etc.) and a cost of “assembly line” which will decide the price. Obviously the mass scale of production of the order of 10^9 units will help to reduce the unit price.

Figure 3. Graphitic sheet in ball representation. The dimensions are $\sim 14\text{\AA} \times 10\text{\AA}$.

4 Drive System

One of the most intriguing features of a nano-car is its drive system. The “engine” is hidden in the wheels. Taft *et al.* [5] reported the first study of magnetic properties of anti-ferromagnetic “ferric wheel”. The wheel contains ten iron atoms located symmetrically and circularly in a molecule. The intra-molecular magnetic interactions of ferric ions were considered by those authors. However it will be most interesting to study magnetic interactions of a “ferric wheel” with external magnetic fields which will cause it to rotate. The external magnetic fields could be due to presence of magnetic domains in atomic substrate (“a road”), spin waves in a substrate, or oscillating magnetic field above the surface. By changing various time- and length- dependent characteristics of an external magnetic field a nano-car will be accelerated, decelerated or manouvered on its path. The details of these interactions are crucial and await more detailed studies.

5 Applications of a nano-car

The applications of a nano-car are many and exhaustive exploration of all possibilities would take us outside the main topic of this paper which is the construction and feasibility study of a nano-car.

Let us briefly list some of the most obvious application areas:

- testing the road rules,
- accident prevention,
- large number of cars models of Intelligent Vehicle Systems,
- traffic simulators of the whole cities (e.g. Mexico City traffic)
- accurate drug delivery
- nano-couriers

A notable example of a very useful application of a nano-car will be its use for efficient

transportation of buckyball molecules (C_{60} , see Figure 4) in building Buckyball Pyramids. Without going into details (which by itself could constitute another report) we just mention rationale for such activity.

Figure 4. Buckyball molecule C_{60}

Each civilisation leaves behind the pyramid fit to its greatness. Examples abound: Egypt, Aztec and Maya civilisations, Pompidou Centre (Paris), Parliament House in Canberra, Australia. Huge and monumental things were done and do not pose the original challenge - XXI century has to be celebrated with *Very Small Pyramids*. Buckyball pyramids will find wide use in a range of areas: from a Christmas season novelty, a collector item (collect them all?), to its use in SETI search and communication with alien civilizations (proving our Civilisation's superior intelligence and ability to control matter) and finally to extensive studies of paranormal claims of pyramid "energy" (through orientation, scale ratios, etc.).

6 Conclusions

The concept of miniaturisation played an important role in development of the modern technological society. We are just on the verge of scientific and technological breakthroughs which will bring the ultimate limit of miniaturisation. Building a nano-car, an enterprise without a doubt worth pursuing, constitutes the ultimate challenge to Automotive Industry, but will necessarily involve chemists, physicists and material scientists.

Philosophical and social implications of this invention are hard to predict. We may only speculate that its size and mass scale of manufacture will make global civilisation more egalitarian and just: perhaps we will see a day when there is one nano-car and one Buckyball pyramid for each and every person. Humankind faces constant challenge and desire to "out-do" earlier generations and contemporaries. The race of nations to dominate the World, so beneficial in bringing about Space exploration, landing of humans on the Moon, or collapse of Communism and the end of The Cold War, is still on. The nation that wins in microscopic world might very well be the nation to win the Globe.

7 Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank the organizers of the 3rd Cray-UNAM conference on "Computational Chemistry and Chemical Engineering" in Mexico City for providing for the most enjoyable atmosphere conducive to free thinking and speculations of any sort. I thank Prof. Diana Guenzburger for bringing the "Molecular Ferric Wheel" to my attention. Ferric wheel molecule was built using Cerius2 program with input parameters from Ref.[5]. All other molecules and molecular fragments were built and optimised using the UniChem suite of Quantum Chemistry programs.

8 References

1. R. Feynman, "There's Plenty of Room at the Bottom", *Engineering and Science* Caltech, Feb. 1960; also at: <http://nano.xerox.com/nanotech/feynman.html>
2. K. Eric Drexler, "Nanosystems: molecular machinery, manufacturing and computation", J. Wiley & Sons, New York, 1992
3. "Nanotechnology: molecular speculations on global abundance", B.C. Crandall, Ed., MIT Press, Cambridge, 1996
4. M. T. Michalewicz, "Rational Nanoelectronic Device Design - A definition of another Grand Challenge problem", High Performance Computing-Asia '95 Electronic Proceedings, National Center For High-Performance Computing, Taiwan, Email: hpc@nchc.gov.tw, also available at: <http://www.mel.dit.csiro.au/~marek/papers.list.html>
5. K.L. Taft, C.D. Delfs, G.C. Papaefthymiou, S. Foner, D. Gatteschi and S.J. Lippard, "[Fe(OMe)₂(O₂CCH₂Cl)]₁₀, a Molecular Ferric Wheel", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **116**, 823-832 (1994)
6. R. Pease, "Nanoworlds are made of this", *New Scientist* 10th June 1995, pp. 26-29
7. R.C. Merkle, "Computational nanotechnology", *Nanotechnology*, **2**, 134-141, 1991
8. J. Michl, P. Kaszynski, A.C. Friedli, G.S. Murthy, H-Ch. Yang, R.E. Robinson, N.D. McMurdie and T. Kim, "Harnessing strain: from [1.1.1]propellanes to tinkertoys", in: "Strain and Its Implications in Organic Chemistry", A. de Meijere and S. Blechert (Eds.), Kluwer Academic, (1989) pp.463-482
9. P. Kaszynski, A.C. Friedli and J. Michl, "Toward a Molecular-Size 'Tinkertoy' Construction Set. Preparation of Terminally Functionalized [n]Staffenes from [1.1.1]Propellane", *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **114** 601-620 (1992)
10. P. Kaszynski, "From [1.1.1]propellane to Tinkertoys", Ph.D. Thesis, University of Texas at Austin, 1991, 342pp.
11. A-D. Schlüter, "Poly([1.1.1]propellane). A Novel Rigid-Rod Polymer Obtained by Ring-Opening Polymerization Breaking a Carbon-Carbon σ -Bond", *Macromolecules*, **21** 1208-1211 (1988)
12. A-D. Schlüter, H. Bothe and J-M Gosau, "[1.1.1]Propellanes. From a hydrocarbon curiosity to a versatile monomer for the synthesis of structurally new polymers", *Macromol. Chem.* **192** 2497-2519 (1991)
13. K. Hassenrück, G.S. Murthy, V.M. Lynch and J. Michl, "'Mixed Staffanes' as Intermediate-Length Staffs for Molecular-Size Tinkertoys. Parent Hydrocarbons and Terminal Diiodides Combining Bicyclo[1.1.1]pentane with Cubane or Bicyclo[2.2.2]octane Units", *J. Org. Chem.* **55**, 1013-1016 (1990)
14. C.B. Musgrave, J.K. Perry, R.C. Merkle and W.A. Goddard III, "Theoretical studies of a hydrogen abstraction tool for nanotechnology", *Nanotechnology*, **2**, 187-195 (1991)